

1 **Nestin is dynamically controlled during lineage commitment in the human embryo.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here dynamic control of
9 Nestin during lineage commitment in the human embryo.

10 Citations

11 1. Brons, I.G.M., Smithers, L.E., Trotter, M.W., Rugg-Gunn, P., Sun, B., Chuva de Sousa Lopes,
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13 pluripotent epiblast stem cells from mammalian embryos. *Nature*, 448(7150), pp.191-195.
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